

Theoretical Equations for the Study of Entropy of Emotions and Enhancing Performance of Artificial Intelligence

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Parametric entropy evaluation

$$= \{x+ix\} + \{\pi^x + i^{\pi^x}\} - \left\{ \left(x^{1/3} + ix \right) \sqrt{x+ix} \right\} \quad \text{Equation (Eq) - 1}$$

In[1]:= $(x + I*x) + (\pi^x + I^{\pi^x}) - (x^{1/3} + I*x)*\text{Sqrt}[x + I*x]$

Out[1]=

$$i^{\pi^x} + \pi^x + (1+i)x - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x}$$

In[2]:= $\{x+ix\} + \{\pi^x + i^{\pi^x}\} - \left\{ \left(x^{1/3} + ix \right) \sqrt{x+ix} \right\}$

Out[2]=

Assuming i is the imaginary unit | Use i as a variable instead

Input: $(x + ix) + (\pi^x + i^{\pi^x}) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + ix) \sqrt{x + ix}$

i is the imaginary unit »

Result: $-\sqrt{(1+i)x} (\sqrt[3]{x} + ix) + i^{\pi^x} + \pi^x + (1+i)x$

Plots:

— $\text{Re}\left(i^{\pi^x} + \pi^x + (1+i)x - (\sqrt[3]{x} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x}\right)$

— $\text{Im}\left(i^{\pi^x} + \pi^x + (1+i)x - (\sqrt[3]{x} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x}\right)$

— real part

— imaginary

min ————— max

min

Alternate form: +

$$-i \left(\sqrt[3]{x} \sqrt{(1+i)x} (x^{2/3} - i) + i^{\pi^x+1} + i\pi^x - (1-i)x \right)$$

Expanded form: Step-by-step solution +

$$-i \sqrt{(1+i)x} x + (1+i)x - \sqrt{(1+i)x} \sqrt[3]{x} + i^{\pi^x} + \pi^x$$

Numerical roots: More digits +

$$x \approx -1.17852 + 0.0882241 i \dots$$

$$x \approx -0.426423 - 1.82279 i \dots$$

$$x \approx 0.524121 - 0.183455 i \dots$$

Series expansion at $x = 0$: +

$$(1+i) - \sqrt{1+i} x^{5/6} + x \left((1+i) + \log(\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \pi \log(\pi) \right) - i \sqrt{1+i} x^{3/2} +$$

$$\frac{1}{8} (4 - 2\pi - i\pi^2) x^2 \log^2(\pi) + \frac{1}{48} (8 - 4\pi - 6i\pi^2 + \pi^3) x^3 \log^3(\pi) +$$

$$\frac{1}{384} (16 - 8\pi - 28i\pi^2 + 12\pi^3 + i\pi^4) x^4 \log^4(\pi) -$$

$$\frac{x^5 \left((-32 + 16\pi + 120i\pi^2 - 100\pi^3 - 20i\pi^4 + \pi^5) \log^5(\pi) \right)}{3840} + O(x^{35/6})$$

(Puiseux series)

[log\(x\) is the natural logarithm »](#)

[Big-O notation »](#)

Series expansion at $x = \infty$: +

$$\left(-\frac{i \sqrt{(1+i)x} x^{3/2}}{\sqrt{x}} + (1+i)x - \frac{\sqrt{(1+i)x} x^{5/6}}{\sqrt{x}} + O\left(\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^{31/6}\right) \right) + i^{\pi^x} + \pi^x$$

[Big-O notation »](#)

Derivative: Approximate form Step-by-step solution +

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left((x+i)x + (\pi^x + i^{\pi^x}) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + ix) \sqrt{x+ix} \right) =$$

$$\frac{1}{6} \left(-\frac{5 \sqrt{(1+i)x}}{x^{2/3}} - 9i \sqrt{(1+i)x} + 6\pi^x \log(\pi) + 3i i^{\pi^x} \pi^{x+1} \log(\pi) + (6+6i) \right)$$

Indefinite integral: +

$$\int (i^{\pi^x} + \pi^x + (1+i)x - (\sqrt[3]{x} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x}) dx =$$

$$\frac{\text{Ei}\left(\frac{1}{2} i \pi^{x+1}\right)}{\log(\pi)} - \frac{6}{11} \sqrt{(1+i)x} x^{4/3} + \left(\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right) - \frac{2}{5} i \sqrt{(1+i)x}\right) x^2 + \frac{\pi^x}{\log(\pi)} + \text{gsrwrerx}$$

Ei(x) is the exponential integral Ei »

WolframAlpha +

gaph{x+ix}+{π^x+i^π^x}-[{x^1/3+ix}*√{x+ix}]

Eq - 1a

In[3]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x) + (Pi^x + I^Pi^x) - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Out[3]=

— $\text{Re}\left(i^{\pi^x} + \pi^x + (1+i)x - (\sqrt[3]{x} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x}\right)$

— $\text{Im}\left(i^{\pi^x} + \pi^x + (1+i)x - (\sqrt[3]{x} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x}\right)$

```
logPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x) + (Pi^x + I^Pi^x) - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]], {x, -6., 6.}]]
```

Eq - 1b

```
In[4]:= LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x) + (Pi^x + I^Pi^x) - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]], {x, -6., 6.}]]
```

Out[4]=


```
graph{x+ix}+{\pi^x+i^{\pi^x}}-{\{x^{1/3}+ix\}*\sqrt{x+ix}}
```

Eq - 1c

```
In[5]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x) + (Pi^x + I^Pi^x) - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]], {x, -6., 6.}]]
```

Out[5]=

Eq - 1d

log plot $\{\text{Re}(-\sqrt{(1+i)x}(x^{1/3}+ix)+i^{\pi^x}+\pi^x+(1+i)x), \text{Im}(-\sqrt{(1+i)x}(x^{1/3}+ix)+i^{\pi^x}+\pi^x+(1+i)x)\}$ from $x = -6.$ to $6.$

Eq - 1d

In[8]:= `LogPlot[{Re[I^Pi^x + Pi^x + (1 + I)*x - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[(1 + I)*x]],
Im[I^Pi^x + Pi^x + (1 + I)*x - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[(1 + I)*x]]}, {x, -6., 6.}]`

Out[8]=

Eq - 1e

Eq - 1e

$\int_0^{\infty} \{\text{Re}(-\sqrt{(1+i)x}(x^{1/3}+ix)+i^{\pi^x}+\pi^x+(1+i)x), \text{Im}(-\sqrt{(1+i)x}(x^{1/3}+ix)+i^{\pi^x}+\pi^x+(1+i)x)\} dx$

Eq - 1e

In[7]:= `Integrate[{Re[I^Pi^x + Pi^x + (1 + I)*x - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[(1 + I)*x]],
Im[I^Pi^x + Pi^x + (1 + I)*x - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[(1 + I)*x]]}, {x, 0, Infinity}]`

Integrate: Integral of $\pi^x + \text{Re}\left[i^{\pi^x} + (1+i)x - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x}\right]$ does not converge on $\{0, \infty\}$.

Integrate: Integral of $\text{Im}\left[i^{\pi^x} + (1+i)x - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x}\right]$ does not converge on $\{0, \infty\}$.

Out[7]=

$\left\{ \int_0^{\infty} \text{Re}\left[i^{\pi^x} + \pi^x + (1+i)x - \left(x^{1/3} + ix\right) \sqrt{(1+i)x}\right] dx, \int_0^{\infty} \text{Im}\left[i^{\pi^x} + \pi^x + (1+i)x - \left(x^{1/3} + ix\right) \sqrt{(1+i)x}\right] dx \right\}$

$$\boxed{\text{Eq - 1f}} \quad \frac{d}{dx} \left\{ \text{Re}(-\sqrt{x(1+i)} (x^{1/3} + ix) + i^{\pi x} + \pi^x + (1+i)x), \right. \\ \left. \text{Im}(-\sqrt{x(1+i)} (x^{1/3} + ix) + i^{\pi x} + \pi^x + (1+i)x) \right\}$$

In[6]:= `D[{Re[I^Pi^x + Pi^x + (1 + I)*x - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[(1 + I)*x]], Im[I^Pi^x + Pi^x + (1 + I)*x - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[(1 + I)*x]], x]`

Out[6]=

$$\left\{ (1+i) - \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)(x^{1/3} + ix)}{\sqrt{(1+i)x}} - \left(i + \frac{1}{3x^{2/3}}\right) \sqrt{(1+i)x} + \pi^x \text{Log}[\pi] + \frac{1}{2} i i^{\pi x} \pi^{1+x} \text{Log}[\pi] \right. \\ \left. \text{Re}\left[i^{\pi x} + \pi^x + (1+i)x - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x}\right], \right. \\ \left. (1+i) - \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)(x^{1/3} + ix)}{\sqrt{(1+i)x}} - \left(i + \frac{1}{3x^{2/3}}\right) \sqrt{(1+i)x} + \pi^x \text{Log}[\pi] + \frac{1}{2} i i^{\pi x} \pi^{1+x} \text{Log}[\pi] \right. \\ \left. \text{Im}\left[i^{\pi x} + \pi^x + (1+i)x - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x}\right] \right\}$$

$$\boxed{\text{Eq - 2}} \quad \text{graph}\{x+ix^2\}+\{\pi^x+i^{\pi x^2}\}-\{x^{1/3}+ix^2\}*\sqrt{x+ix^2}$$

Eq - 2

In[9]:= `Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2) + (Pi^x + I^Pi^x^2) - (x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]], {x, -6., 6.}]`

Out[9]=

$$\boxed{\text{Eq - 2a}} \quad \{-\text{Im}(x^2) + \text{Re}(i^{\pi(x^2)}) - (x^{1/3} + i x^2) \sqrt{x + i x^2} + x + \pi^x, \text{Re}(x^2) + \text{Im}(i^{\pi(x^2)}) - (x^{1/3} + i x^2) \sqrt{x + i x^2} + x + \pi^x\}$$

Eq - 2a

In[11]:=
$$\{-\text{Im}[x^2] + \text{Re}[I^{\wedge}\text{Pi}^{\wedge}x^{\wedge}2 + \text{Pi}^{\wedge}x + x - (x^{1/3} + I*x^{\wedge}2)*\text{Sqrt}[x + I*x^{\wedge}2]],$$

$$\text{Im}[I^{\wedge}\text{Pi}^{\wedge}x^{\wedge}2 + \text{Pi}^{\wedge}x + x - (x^{1/3} + I*x^{\wedge}2)*\text{Sqrt}[x + I*x^{\wedge}2]] + \text{Re}[x^{\wedge}2]\}$$

Out[11]=

$$\{-\text{Im}[x^2] + \text{Re}[i^{\pi x^2} + \pi^x + x - (x^{1/3} + i x^2) \sqrt{x + i x^2}], \text{Im}[i^{\pi x^2} + \pi^x + x - (x^{1/3} + i x^2) \sqrt{x + i x^2}] + \text{Re}[x^2]\}$$

$$\boxed{\text{Eq - 2b}} \quad \text{LogPlot}[\text{Evaluate}[\text{ReIm}[(x + I*x^2) + (\text{Pi}^x + I^{\wedge}\text{Pi}^{\wedge}x^2) - (x^{1/3} + I*x^2)*\text{Sqrt}[x + I*x^2]]], \{x, -6., 6.\}]$$

Eq - 2b

In[10]:=
$$\text{LogPlot}[\text{Evaluate}[\text{ReIm}[(x + I*x^2) + (\text{Pi}^x + I^{\wedge}\text{Pi}^{\wedge}x^2) - (x^{1/3} + I*x^2)*\text{Sqrt}[x + I*x^2]]], \{x, -6., 6.\}]$$

Out[10]=

— $-\text{Im}(x^2) + \text{Re}(i^{\pi x^2} + \pi^x + x - (\sqrt[3]{x} + i x^2) \sqrt{x + i x^2})$;
 — $\text{Im}(i^{\pi x^2} + \pi^x + x - (\sqrt[3]{x} + i x^2) \sqrt{x + i x^2}) +$

Eq - 3 graph $\{x+ix\}\sin x + \{\pi^x + i^{\pi^x}\}\tan x - \{(x^{1/3} + ix) \cdot \sqrt{x+ix}\}\sin x$

Eq - 3

In[12]:=

```
Plot[
  Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*Sin[x] + (Pi^x + I^Pi^x)*Tan[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x])*Sin[x]],
  {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[12]:=

Eq - 3a Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*Csc[x] + (Pi^x + I^Pi^x)*Cot[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x])*Csc[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Eq - 3a

In[15]:=

```
Plot[
  Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*Csc[x] + (Pi^x + I^Pi^x)*Cot[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x])*Csc[x]],
  {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[15]:=


```
Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*ArcSin[x] + (Pi^x + I^Pi^x)*ArcTan[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x])*ArcSin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Eq - 3b

In[14]:=

```
Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*ArcSin[x] + (Pi^x + I^Pi^x)*ArcTan[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x])*ArcSin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[14]=


```
LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*Sin[x] + (Pi^x + I^Pi^x)*Tan[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x])*Sin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Eq - 3c

In[13]:=

```
LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*Sin[x] + (Pi^x + I^Pi^x)*Tan[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x])*Sin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[13]=

$$\{d^2 x / dt^2\} + \{d^2 \pi^x / dt^2\} - \{d^2 \sqrt{x} / dt^2\} * \{d^2 x^{1/3} / dt^2\} \quad \text{Eq - 4}$$

$$\text{In[1]:= } D[x, \{t, 2\}] + D[\text{Pi}^x, \{t, 2\}] - D[\text{Sqrt}[x], \{t, 2\}] * (d^2 * (x^{1/3} / dt^2))$$

Out[1]=

$$0 / dt^2$$

$$\{d^2 x / dt^2\} + \{d^2 \pi^x / dt^2\} - \{d^2 \sqrt{x} / dt^2\} - \{d^2 x^3 / dt^2\} \quad \text{Eq - 5}$$

$$\text{In[3]:= } D[x, \{t, 2\}] + D[\text{Pi}^x, \{t, 2\}] - D[\text{Sqrt}[x], \{t, 2\}] - d^2 * (x^3 / dt^2)$$

Out[3]=

$$d^2 x^3 (-1 / dt^2)$$

$$\text{In[5]:= } \{d^2 x / dt^2\} + \{d^2 \pi^x / dt^2\} - \{d^2 \sqrt{x} / dt^2\} - \{d^2 x^3 / dt^2\}$$

Out[5]=

Input interpretation:

$$x''(t) + \frac{\partial^2 \pi^x}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \sqrt{x}}{\partial t^2} - d^2 \times \frac{x^3}{dt^2 \text{ (metric deciton squared)}}$$

Result:

$$d^2 x^3 - 1 / dt^2 \text{ (per metric deciton squared)} + x''(t)$$

WolframAlpha

$$\text{In[4]:= } \partial_x \left(d^2 x^3 \text{Quantity}[-1, \frac{1}{\text{"MetricDecitons"}^2}] \right)$$

Out[4]=

$$d^2 x^2 (-3 / dt^2)$$

$$\{d^2x/dt^2\} + \{d^2e^x/dt^2\} - \{d^2\sqrt{x}/dt^2\} * \{d^2x^{1/3}/dt^2\}$$

Eq - 6

In[6]:= $D[x, \{t, 2\}] + D[E^x, \{t, 2\}] - D[\text{Sqrt}[x], \{t, 2\}] * (d^2 * (x^{1/3}) / dt^2)$

Out[6]=

$$0 / dt^2$$

Out[12]=

Input interpretation: +

$$x''(t) + \frac{\partial^2 e^x}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \sqrt{x}}{\partial t^2} \left(d^2 \times \frac{\sqrt[3]{x}}{dt^5 \text{ (metric deciton squared)}} \right)$$

Result: +

$$x''(t)$$

Series expansion at t = 0: +

$$x''(0) + t x^{(3)}(0) + \frac{1}{2} t^2 x^{(4)}(0) + \frac{1}{6} t^3 x^{(5)}(0) + \frac{1}{24} t^4 x^{(6)}(0) + O(t^5)$$

(Taylor series)

[Big-O notation »](#)Derivative: +

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(x''(t) + \frac{\partial^2 e^x}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\frac{\partial^2 \sqrt{x}}{\partial t^2} (d^2 \sqrt[3]{x})}{dt^6 \text{ (metric deciton squared)}} \right) = x^{(3)}(t)$$

WolframAlpha +

In[11]:=

$$\{d^2x/dt^2\} + \{d^2e^x/dt^2\} - \{d^2\sqrt{x}/dt^2\} * \{d^2x^{1/3}/dt^2\}$$

Out[11]=

Input interpretation: +

$$x''(t) + \frac{\partial^2 e^x}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \sqrt{x}}{\partial t^2} \left(d^2 \times \frac{\sqrt[3]{x}}{dt^6 \text{ (metric deciton squared)}} \right)$$

Result: +

$$x''(t)$$

Series expansion at t = 0: +

$$x''(0) + t x^{(3)}(0) + \frac{1}{2} t^2 x^{(4)}(0) + \frac{1}{6} t^3 x^{(5)}(0) + \frac{1}{24} t^4 x^{(6)}(0) + O(t^5)$$

(Taylor series)

[Big-O notation »](#)Derivative: +

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(x''(t) + \frac{\partial^2 e^x}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\frac{\partial^2 \sqrt{x}}{\partial t^2} (d^2 \sqrt[3]{x})}{dt^6 \text{ (metric deciton squared)}} \right) = x^{(3)}(t)$$

WolframAlpha +

$$\text{Eq - 7} \quad \{dx/dt \sin x\} + \{d^2 e^x / dt^2\} - \{d^2 \sqrt{x} / dt^2\} * \{d^3 x^3 / dt^3\}$$

In[13]:= $D[x, t] * \sin[x] + D[E^x, \{t, 2\}] - D[\text{Sqrt}[x], \{t, 2\}] * (d^3 * (x^3 / dt^3))$

Out[13]= $\emptyset / dt^3$

$$\text{Eq - 8} \quad \{d(x+ix)/dt \sin(x+ix)\} + \{d^2(e^x+ix)/dt^2\} - \{d^2(x+ix)/dt^2\} * \{d^3(x+ix)^3/dt^3\}$$

In[16]:= $D[x + I*x, t] * \sin[x + I*x] + D[E^x + I*x, \{t, 2\}] - D[x + I*x, \{t, 2\}] * (d^3 * ((x + I*x)^3 / dt^3))$

Out[16]= $\emptyset / dt^3$

In[17]:=

$$\{d(x+ix)/dt \sin(x+ix) + \{d^2(e^x+ix)/dt^2\} - [\{d^2(x+ix)/dt^2\} * \{d^3(x+ix)^3/dt^3\}]$$

Out[17]=

Assuming i is the imaginary unit | Use i as a **variable** instead

Input interpretation: +

$$\frac{\partial(x+ix)}{\partial t} \sin(x+ix) + \frac{\partial^2(e^x+ix)}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2(x+ix)}{\partial t^2} \left(d^3 \times \frac{(x+ix)^3}{dt^7 \text{ (metric deciton cubed)}} \right)$$

i is the imaginary unit »

Result: +

0

WolframAlpha +

$$\{x+ix\} \sin x + \{e^x + i e^x\} \tan x - \{x^{1/3} + ix\} * \sqrt{\{x+ix\} \sin x}$$

Eq - 9

In[1]:=

$$(x + I*x)*\text{Sin}[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*\text{Tan}[x] - (x^{1/3} + I*x)*\text{Sqrt}[x + I*x]*\text{Sin}[x]$$

Out[1]=

$$(1+i)x \sin(x) - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x} \sin(x) + (e^x + i e^x) \tan(x)$$

In[2]:=

$$\{x+ix\} \sin x + \{e^x + i e^x\} \tan x - \{x^{1/3} + ix\} * \sqrt{\{x+ix\} \sin x}$$

Out[2]=

Assuming i is the imaginary unit | Use i as a **variable** instead

Input: +

$$(x+ix) \sin(x) + (e^x + i e^x) \tan(x) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + ix) \sqrt{x+ix} \sin(x)$$

i is the imaginary unit »

Result: +

$$(1+i)x \sin(x) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x} \sin(x) + (e^x + i e^x) \tan(x)$$

Plots: +

min max

min max

Alternate forms:

More

$$(1+i)x \sin(x) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x \sin(x)} + \frac{(i^{e^x} + e^x) \sin(x)}{\cos(x)}$$

$$(-i \sqrt[3]{x} ((x^{2/3} - i) \sqrt{(1+i)x} - (1-i)x^{2/3}) \cos(x) + i^{e^x} + e^x) \tan(x)$$

$$\sin\left(\frac{x}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{x}{2}\right) (i^{e^x} + e^x + (1+i)x \cos(x) - ix \sqrt{(1+i)x} \cos(x) - \sqrt[3]{x} \sqrt{(1+i)x} \cos(x))$$

$$\csc\left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{x}{2}\right) \csc\left(\frac{x}{2} + \frac{\pi}{4}\right)$$

$\csc(x)$ is the cosecant function [»](#)

Expanded form:

$$(1+i)x \sin(x) - ix \sqrt{(1+i)x} \sin(x) - \sqrt[3]{x} \sqrt{(1+i)x} \sin(x) + i^{e^x} \tan(x) + e^x \tan(x)$$

Derivative:

Approximate form

Step-by-step solution

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left((x+i x) \sin(x) + (e^x + i^{e^x}) \tan(x) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x} \sin(x) \right) =$$

$$(1+i) \sin(x) + (e^x + i^{e^x}) \sec^2(x) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x} \cos(x) - \sqrt[3]{x} \sqrt{(1+i)x} \sin(x)$$

$$-\left(\frac{1}{3x^{2/3}} + i\right) \sqrt{(1+i)x} \sin(x) - \frac{(2+i)\sqrt{(1+i)x} \sin(x)}{\sqrt{(1+i)x}} + (1+i) \sin(x) + (1+i)x \cos(x) -$$

$$(\sqrt[3]{x} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x} \cos(x) + \left(e^x + \frac{1}{2} i \pi i^{e^x} e^x\right) \tan(x) + (e^x + i^{e^x}) \sec^2(x)$$

sec(x) is the secant function »

WolframAlpha

graph{x+ix}sinx+{e^x+i^e^x}tanx-[(x^1/3+ix)*sqrt{x+ix}sinx] Eq - 9a

```
In[3]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*Tan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*Sin[x]],
{x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[3]=


```
Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*Csc[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*Cot[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*Csc[x]]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Eq - 9b

```
In[10]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*Csc[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*Cot[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*Csc[x]]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[10]=


```
Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*ArcSin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*ArcTan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*ArcSin[x]]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Eq - 9c

```
In[9]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*ArcSin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*ArcTan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*ArcSin[x]]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[9]=

E `Plot[Conjugate[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*Tan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*Sin[x]]], {x, -6., 6.}]`

Eq - 9d

In[8]:= `Plot[Conjugate[
Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*Tan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*Sin[x]]], {x,
-6., 6.}]`

Out[8]=

E domain of $(\text{Re}((1 + i)x \sin(x) - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1 + i)x \sin(x) + (e^x + i^{e^x}) \tan(x)}), \text{Im}((1 + i)x \sin(x) - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1 + i)x \sin(x) + (e^x + i^{e^x}) \tan(x)}))$ Eq - 9e

In[7]:= `FunctionDomain[{Re[(1 + I)*x*Ssin[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[(1 + I)*x]*Sin[x] + (I^E^x + E^x)*Tan[x],
Im[(1 + I)*x*Ssin[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[(1 + I)*x]*Sin[x] + (I^E^x + E^x)*Tan[x]]}, {x}]`

Out[7]=

False

```
LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*Tan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*Sin[x]]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Eq - 9f

```
In[5]:= LogPlot[Evaluate[
  ReIm[(x + I*x)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*Tan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*Sin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```



```
In[4]:= graph{x+ix}sinx+{e^x+i^e^x}tanx-[{x^1/3+ix}*sqrt{x+ix}sinx]
```

Out[4]=

Assuming i is the imaginary unit | Use i as a variable instead

Input interpretation: +

plot $(x + i x) \sin(x) + (e^x + i^{e^x}) \tan(x) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + i x) \sqrt{x + i x} \sin(x)$

i is the imaginary unit »

Plots: +

min max

min max

$$\{x+ix^2\}\sin x + \{e^x + i e^{x^2}\}\tan x - \{x^{1/3} + ix^2\} \sqrt{x+ix^2} \sin x$$

Eq - 10

$$\text{In[11]:= } (x + I*x^2)*\text{Sin}[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*\text{Tan}[x] - (x^{1/3} + I*x^2)*\text{Sqrt}[x + I*x^2]*\text{Sin}[x]$$

$$\text{Out[11]:= } -\left((x^{1/3} + i x^2) \sqrt{x + i x^2} \sin(x)\right) + (x + i x^2) \sin(x) + (i^{e^{i^2}} + e^x) \tan(x)$$

$$\text{In[12]:= } \{x+ix^2\}\sin x + \{e^x + i e^{x^2}\}\tan x - \{x^{1/3} + ix^2\} \sqrt{x+ix^2} \sin x$$

Out[12]=

Assuming i is the imaginary unit | Use i as a **variable** instead

Input:

$$(x + i x^2) \sin(x) + (e^D + i e^{x^2}) \tan(x) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + i x^2) \sqrt{x + i x^2} \sin(x)$$

i is the imaginary unit »

Plots:

min max

Alternate forms:

More +

$$\left(-i\left(\sqrt[3]{x}\sqrt{i x(x-i)}\right)\left(x^{5/3}-i\right)-x(x-i)\right)\cos(x)+i^{e^{x^2}}+e^x)\tan(x)$$

$$-\left(\sqrt[3]{x}+i x^2\right)\sqrt{x+i x^2}\sin(x)+\left(x+i x^2\right)\sin(x)+\frac{\left(i^{e^{x^2}}+e^x\right)\sin(x)}{\cos(x)}$$

$$\sin\left(\frac{x}{2}\right)\cos\left(\frac{x}{2}\right)$$

$$\left(i^{e^{x^2}}-i\sqrt{i x(x-i)}\right)x^2\cos(x)+i x^2\cos(x)+e^x+x\cos(x)-\sqrt{i x(x-i)}\sqrt[3]{x}\cos(x)$$

$$\csc\left(\frac{\pi}{4}-\frac{x}{2}\right)\csc\left(\frac{x}{2}+\frac{\pi}{4}\right)$$

csc(x) is the cosecant function »

Expanded form:

+

$$-i\sqrt{x+i x^2}x^2\sin(x)+i x^2\sin(x)-\sqrt{x+i x^2}\sqrt[3]{x}\sin(x)+i^{e^{x^2}}\tan(x)+x\sin(x)+e^x\tan(x)$$

Derivative:

Approximate form

Step-by-step solution +

$$\frac{d}{dx}\left(\left(x+i x^2\right)\sin(x)+\left(e^x+i^{e^{x^2}}\right)\tan(x)-\left(\sqrt[3]{x}+i x^2\right)\sqrt{x+i x^2}\sin(x)\right)=$$

$$-\frac{(1+2 i x)\left(\sqrt[3]{x}+i x^2\right)\sin(x)}{2\sqrt{x+i x^2}}+(x+i x^2)\cos(x)-$$

$$\left(\sqrt[3]{x}+i x^2\right)\sqrt{x+i x^2}\cos(x)+\left(e^x+\pi i^{e^{x^2}+1}e^{x^2}x\right)\tan(x)+$$

$$\left(e^x+i^{e^{x^2}}\right)\sec^2(x)-\left(\frac{1}{3 x^{2/3}}+2 i x\right)\sqrt{x+i x^2}\sin(x)+(1+2 i x)\sin(x)$$

sec(x) is the secant function »WolframAlpha +

graph{x+ix^2}sinx+{e^x+i^e^x^2}tanx-[(x^1/3+ix^2)*sqrt{x+ix^2}sinx]

Eq - 10

```
In[13]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*Sin[x] +
  (E^x + I^E^x^2)*Tan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*Sin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[13]=

In[21]=

 graph{x+ix^2}sinx+{e^x+i^e^x^2}tanx-{{x^1/3+ix^2}*sqrt{x+ix^2}sinx}

Out[21]=

Assuming i is the imaginary unit | Use i as a variable instead

Input interpretation:

plot $(x + i x^2) \sin(x) + (e^x + i e^{x^2}) \tan(x) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + i x^2) \sqrt{x + i x^2} \sin(x)$

i is the imaginary unit »

Plots:

Eq - 10a
 $\text{log plot } \{ \text{Re}((x + i x^2) \sin(x) - (x^{1/3} + i x^2) \sqrt{x + i x^2} \sin(x) + (e^x + i^{(e^x)}) \tan(x)), \text{Im}((x + i x^2) \sin(x) - (x^{1/3} + i x^2) \sqrt{x + i x^2} \sin(x) + (e^x + i^{(e^x)}) \tan(x)) \}$ from $x = -6.$ to $6.$

In[20]:=

```

LogPlot[
{Re[-((x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2])*Sin[x] + (x + I*x^2)*Sin[x] + (I^E^x + E^x)*Tan[x],
Im[-((x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2])*Sin[x] +
(x + I*x^2)*Sin[x] + (I^E^x + E^x)*Tan[x]}], {x, -6., 6.}]

```

Out[20]=

Eq - 10b
 $\text{Plot[Evaluate[ReIm}[(x + I*x^2)*Csc[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*Cot[x] - (x^{1/3} + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*Csc[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]$

In[19]:=

```

Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*Csc[x] +
(E^x + I^E^x^2)*Cot[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*Csc[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]

```

Out[19]=


```

Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*ArcSin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*ArcTan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*ArcSin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]]
Eq - 10c

```

```

In[18]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*ArcSin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*ArcTan[x] -
(x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*ArcSin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]

```

Out[18]=


```

Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*Cos[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*Tan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*Cos[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]]
Eq - 10d

```

```

In[17]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*Cos[x] +
(E^x + I^E^x^2)*Tan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*Cos[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]

```

Out[17]=

E Plot[Conjugate[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*Tan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*Sin[x]]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Eq - 10e

In[16]:= Plot[Conjugate[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*Tan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*Sin[x]]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Out[16]=

E domain of (Re((x + i x^2) sin(x) - (x^(1/3) + i x^2) sqrt(x + i x^2) sin(x) + (e^x + i^(e^(x^2))) tan(x)), Im((x + i x^2) sin(x) - (x^(1/3) + i x^2) sqrt(x + i x^2) sin(x) + (e^x + i^(e^(x^2))) tan(x)))

Eq - 10f

In[15]:= FunctionDomain[
 {Re[-((x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*Sin[x] + (x + I*x^2)*Sin[x] + (I^E^x^2 + E^x)*Tan[x]),
 Im[-((x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*Sin[x] + (x + I*x^2)*Sin[x] + (I^E^x^2 + E^x)*Tan[x])], {x}]

Out[15]=

False

```
LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*Tan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*Sin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Eq - 10g

In[14]:=

```
LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*Tan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*Sin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[14]=

$$\{x+ix^3\}\sin x + \{e^x + i^e x^3\}\tan x - \{x^{1/3} + ix^3\} \sqrt{x+ix^3} \sin x$$

Eq - 11

$$\text{In[1]:= } (x + I*x^3)*\text{Sin}[x] + (E^x + I^E*x^3)*\text{Tan}[x] - (x^{1/3} + I*x^3)*\text{Sqrt}[x + I*x^3]*\text{Sin}[x]$$

Out[1]=

$$-\left((x^{1/3} + ix^3) \sqrt{x+ix^3} \sin(x)\right) + (x+ix^3) \sin(x) + (i^{e^{x^3}} + e^x) \tan(x)$$

$$\text{In[2]:= } \{x+ix^3\}\sin x + \{e^x + i^e x^3\}\tan x - \{x^{1/3} + ix^3\} \sqrt{x+ix^3} \sin x$$

Out[2]=

Assuming i is the imaginary unit | Use i as a **variable** instead

Input:

$$(x + ix^3) \sin(x) + (e^x + i^{e^{x^3}}) \tan(x) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + ix^3) \sqrt{x + ix^3} \sin(x)$$

i is the imaginary unit »

Plots:

min max

min max

Alternate forms:

More

$$\left(i^{e^{x^3}} - i \left(\sqrt[3]{x} \sqrt{i x (x^2 - i)} (x^{8/3} - i) - x(x^2 - i)\right)\right) \cos(x) + e^x \tan(x)$$

$$-\left(\sqrt[3]{x} + i x^3\right) \sqrt{x + i x^3} \sin(x) + (x + i x^3) \sin(x) + \frac{\left(i^{e^{x^3}} + e^x\right) \sin(x)}{\cos(x)}$$

$$\sin\left(\frac{x}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{x}{2}\right)$$

$$\left(i^{e^{x^3}} + i x^3 \cos(x) - \sqrt{i x (x^2 - i)} \sqrt[3]{x} \cos(x) - i \sqrt{i x (x^2 - i)} x^3 \cos(x) + e^x + x \cos(x)\right)$$

$$\csc\left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{x}{2}\right) \csc\left(\frac{x}{2} + \frac{\pi}{4}\right)$$

[csc\(x\) is the cosecant function](#)

Expanded form:

$$-i \sqrt{x + i x^3} x^3 \sin(x) + i x^3 \sin(x) - \sqrt{x + i x^3} \sqrt[3]{x} \sin(x) + i^{e^{x^3}} \tan(x) + x \sin(x) + e^x \tan(x)$$

Derivative:

[Approximate form](#)

[Step-by-step solution](#)

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left((x + i x^3) \sin(x) + (e^x + i^{e^{x^3}}) \tan(x) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + i x^3) \sqrt{x + i x^3} \sin(x) \right) =$$

$$(x + i x^3) \cos(x) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + i x^3) \sqrt{x + i x^3} \cos(x) +$$

$$\left(e^x + i^{e^{x^3}}\right) \sec^2(x) + (1 + 3 i x^2) \sin(x) - \frac{(1 + 3 i x^2) (\sqrt[3]{x} + i x^3) \sin(x)}{2 \sqrt{x + i x^3}} +$$

$$\left(e^x + \frac{3}{2} i \pi i^{e^{x^3}} e^{x^3} x^2\right) \tan(x) - \left(\frac{1}{3 x^{2/3}} + 3 i x^2\right) \sqrt{x + i x^3} \sin(x)$$

[sec\(x\) is the secant function](#)

WolframAlpha

graph{x+ix^3}sinx+{e^x+i^e^x^3}tanx-[(x^1/3+ix^3)*sqrt{x+ix^3}sinx]

Eq - 11a

In[3]:=

```
Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*Sin[x] +
(E^x + I^E^x^3)*Tan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*Sin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[3]=


```

Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*Csc[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*Cot[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*
  Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*Csc[x]]], {x, -6., 6.}]

```

Eq - 11b

In[8]:=

```

Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*Csc[x] +
  (E^x + I^E^x^3)*Cot[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*Csc[x]]], {x, -6., 6.}]

```

Out[8]=

Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*ArcSin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*ArcTan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*ArcSin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}] Eq - 11c

In[6]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*ArcSin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*ArcTan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*ArcSin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Out[6]=


```
LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*Tan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*Sin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Eq - 11d

```
In[5]:= LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*Sin[x] +
(E^x + I^E^x^3)*Tan[x] - (x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*Sin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[5]=


```
In[4]:= graph{x+ix^3}sinx+{e^x+i^e^x^3}tanx-[{x^1/3+ix^3}*sqrt{x+ix^3}sinx] Eq - 11e
```

Out[4]=

Assuming i is the imaginary unit | Use i as a **variable** instead

Input interpretation:

plot $(x + i x^3) \sin(x) + (e^x + i e^{x^3}) \tan(x) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + i x^3) \sqrt{x + i x^3} \sin(x)$

i is the imaginary unit »

Plots:

min max

min max

 graph{x+ix^3}sinx+{e^x+i^e^x^3}tanx-[{x^3+ix^3}*\sqrt{x+ix^3}sinx]

Eq - 11f

In[9]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*Sin[x] +
(E^x + I^E^x^3)*Tan[x] - (x^3 + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*Sin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Out[9]=

In[10]:=

 graph{x+ix^3}sinx+{e^x+i^e^x^3}tanx-[{x^3+ix^3}*\sqrt{x+ix^3}sinx]

Out[10]=

Assuming i is the imaginary unit | Use i as a variable insteadInput interpretation: +

plot $(x + ix^0) \sin(x) + (e^x + ie^{x^3}) \tan(x) - (x^0 + ix^0) \sqrt{x + ix^0} \sin(x)$

 i is the imaginary unit »Plots: +WolframAlpha +

Eq - 11g graph $\{x+ix^3\}\sin x+\{e^x+i^e^x^3\}\tan x-\{(x^{1/3}+ix^3)*\sqrt{\{x+ix^3\}\sin x}\}^2$

Eq - 11g

In[11]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*Tan[x] -
((x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*Sin[x]^2)], {x, -6., 6.}]

Out[11]=

Eq - 11h Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*Csc[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*Cot[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*
Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*Csc[x]^2)], {x, -6., 6.}]

Eq - 11h

In[15]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*Csc[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*Cot[x] -
((x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*Csc[x]^2)], {x, -6., 6.}]

Out[15]=

Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*ArcSin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*ArcTan[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*ArcSin[x]^2]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Eq - 11i

In[14]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*ArcSin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*ArcTan[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*ArcSin[x]^2]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Out[14]=

LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*Tan[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*Sin[x]^2)], {x, -6., 6.}]

Eq - 11j

In[13]:= LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*Tan[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*Sin[x]^2)], {x, -6., 6.}]

Out[13]=

In[12]:=

graph{x+ix^3}sinx+{e^x+i^e^x^3}tanx-{{x^1/3+ix^3}*sqrt{x+ix^3}sinx]^2 Eq - 12

Out[12]=

Assuming i is the imaginary unit | Use i as a variable instead

Input interpretation:

plot $(x + i x^0) \sin(x) + (e^x + i e^{x^3}) \tan(x) - ((\sqrt[3]{x} + i x^0) \sqrt{x + i x^0} \sin(x))'$

i is the imaginary unit »

Plots:

Eq - 12a

Eq - 12a

In[16]:=

```
Plot[
  Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*Tan[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*Sin[x]^2)],
  {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[16]=

Eq - 12b

Eq - 12b

In[20]:=

```
Plot[
  Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*Csc[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*Cot[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*Csc[x]^2)],
  {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[20]=

Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*ArcSin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*ArcTan[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*ArcSin[x])^2]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Eq - 12c

In[19]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*ArcSin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*ArcTan[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*ArcSin[x])^2]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Out[19]=

LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*Tan[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*Sin[x])^2]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Eq - 12d

In[18]:= LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*Tan[x] - ((x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*Sin[x])^2]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Out[18]=

In[17]:=

graph{x+ix}sinx+{e^x+i^e^x}tanx-[{x^1/3+ix}]*√{x+ix}sinx]^2 Eq - 12e

Out[17]=

Assuming i is the imaginary unit | Use i as a **variable** insteadInput interpretation: +

plot $(x + ix) \sin(x) + (e^x + i^{e^x}) \tan(x) - ((\sqrt[3]{x} + ix) \sqrt{x + ix} \sin(x))'$

i is the imaginary unit »

Plots: +

min max

min max

WolframAlpha +

graph[[x+ix^3]sinx+{e^x+i^e^x^3}tanx]^2-[(x^1/3+ix^3)*√{x+ix^3}sinx]

Eq - 13

In[21]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[((x + I*x^3)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*Tan[x])^2 -
(x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*Sin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Out[21]=

graph[[x+ix]sinx+{e^x+i^e^x}tanx]^2-[(x^1/3+ix)*√{x+ix}sinx]

Eq - 14

In[22]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[((x + I*x)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*Tan[x])^2 - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*Sin[x]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Out[22]=

E Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[((x + I*x)*Csc[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*Cot[x])^2 - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*Csc[x]]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Eq - 14a

In[27]:=

```
Plot[
  Evaluate[ReIm[((x + I*x)*Csc[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*Cot[x])^2 - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*Csc[x]]],
  {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[27]=

E Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[((x + I*x)*ArcSin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*ArcTan[x])^2 - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*ArcSin[x]]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Eq - 14b

In[26]:=

```
Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[((x + I*x)*ArcSin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*ArcTan[x])^2 -
  (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*ArcSin[x]]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[26]=

E LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[((x + I*x)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*Tan[x])^2 - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*Sin[x]]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Eq - 14c

In[24]:=

```
LogPlot[
  Evaluate[ReIm[((x + I*x)*Sin[x] + (E^x + I^E^x)*Tan[x])^2 - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*Sin[x]],
  {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[24]=

In[23]:=

E graph[{x+ix}sinx + {e^x+i^e^x}tanx]^2 - [{x^1/3+ix}*sqrt{x+ix}sinx]

Out[23]=

Assuming i is the imaginary unit | Use i as a **variable** instead

Input interpretation: +

plot $((x + i x) \sin(x) + (e^x + i e^x) \tan(x))^2 - (\sqrt[3]{x} + i x) \sqrt{x + i x} \sin(x)$

i is the imaginary unit »

Plots: +

— $\text{Re}\left(-\left(\sqrt[3]{x} + i x\right) \sqrt{(1 + i) x} \sin(x)\right) + (1$
 — $\text{Im}\left(-\left(\sqrt[3]{x} + i x\right) \sqrt{(1 + i) x} \sin(x)\right) + (1$

min max

— $\text{Re}\left(-\left(\sqrt[3]{x} + i x\right) \sqrt{(1 + i) x} \sin(x)\right) + (1$
 — $\text{Im}\left(-\left(\sqrt[3]{x} + i x\right) \sqrt{(1 + i) x} \sin(x)\right) + (1$

min max

$$\boxed{\{(x+ix)\{\sin x+i \tan x\}+\{e^x+i e^x\}\{\tan x+i \sin x\}-\{x^{1/3}+ix\}*\sqrt{x+ix}\{\sin x+i \tan x\}\}} \quad \text{Eq - 15}$$

$$\text{In[1]:= } (x + I*x)*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x)*(Tan[x] + I*Sin[x]) - (x^{1/3} + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x])$$

Out[1]=

$$(1 + i)x (\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1 + i)x} (\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) + (i e^x + e^x) (i \sin(x) + \tan(x))$$

$$\text{In[2]:= } \star \quad \boxed{\{(x+ix)\{\sin x+i \tan x\}+\{e^x+i e^x\}\{\tan x+i \sin x\}-\{x^{1/3}+ix\}*\sqrt{x+ix}\{\sin x+i \tan x\}\}}$$

Out[2]=

Assuming i is the imaginary unit | Use i as a **variable** instead

Input:

$$(x + i x) (\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) + (e^x + i e^x) (\tan(x) + i \sin(x)) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + i x) \sqrt{x + i x} (\sin(x) + i \tan(x))$$

i is the imaginary unit »

Result:

$$(1 + i)x (\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + i x) \sqrt{(1 + i)x} (\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) + (e^x + i e^x) (\tan(x) + i \sin(x))$$

Plots:

min max

min max

Alternate forms:

More

$$\sqrt{(1+i)x} (x - i \sqrt[3]{x}) (\tan(x) - i \sin(x)) + (e^x + i e^x) (\tan(x) + i \sin(x)) + (1+i)x (\cos(x) + i) \tan(x)$$

$$(1+i)x \left(\sin(x) + \frac{i \sin(x)}{\cos(x)} \right) -$$

$$\left(\sqrt[3]{x} + i x \right) \sqrt{(1+i)x} \left(\sin(x) + \frac{i \sin(x)}{\cos(x)} \right) + (i e^x + e^x) \left(i \sin(x) + \frac{\sin(x)}{\cos(x)} \right)$$

$$\left(\sqrt[3]{x} \sqrt{(1+i)x} (x^{2/3} - i) - i \left(\sqrt[3]{x} \sqrt{(1+i)x} (x^{2/3} - i) + i^{e^x+2} - e^x - (1-i)x \cos(x) + i e^x + e^x - (1-i)x \tan(x) \right) \right)$$

Expanded form:

$$i^{e^x+1} \sin(x) + i e^x \sin(x) + (1+i)x \sin(x) - i x \sqrt{(1+i)x} \sin(x) - \sqrt[3]{x} \sqrt{(1+i)x} \sin(x) + i^{e^x} \tan(x) + e^x \tan(x) - (1-i)x \tan(x) + x \sqrt{(1+i)x} \tan(x) - i \sqrt[3]{x} \sqrt{(1+i)x} \tan(x)$$

Alternate form assuming $x > 0$:

$$\sqrt{1+i} (x^{2/3} - i) x^{5/6} (1 - i \cos(x)) \tan(x) + (e^x + i e^x) (\tan(x) + i \sin(x)) + (1+i)x (\cos(x) + i) \tan(x)$$

WolframAlpha

graph[{x+ix}{sinx+itanx}+{e^x+i^e^x}{tanx+isinx}-{x^1/3+ix}*sqrt{x+ix}{sinx+itanx}] Eq - 15a

```
In[3]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x)*(Tan[x] + I*Sin[x]) -
(x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x])]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[3]=

$$\boxed{= \frac{d}{dx} \left\{ \operatorname{Re}((1+i)x(\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x(\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) + (e^x + i^{e^x})(\tan(x) + i \sin(x))}, \right.} \quad \text{Eq - 15b}$$

$$\left. \operatorname{Im}((1+i)x(\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x(\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) + (e^x + i^{e^x})(\tan(x) + i \sin(x))} \right\}}$$

In[8]:=

$$D[\{\operatorname{Re}[(1 + I)*x*(\sin[x] + I*\tan[x]) - (x^{1/3} + I*x)*\sqrt{(1 + I)*x*(\sin[x] + I*\tan[x]) + (I^{\wedge}E^{\wedge}x + E^{\wedge}x)*(I*\sin[x] + \tan[x])}], \operatorname{Im}[(1 + I)*x*(\sin[x] + I*\tan[x]) - (x^{1/3} + I*x)*\sqrt{(1 + I)*x*(\sin[x] + I*\tan[x]) + (I^{\wedge}E^{\wedge}x + E^{\wedge}x)*(I*\sin[x] + \tan[x])}], x]$$

Out[8]=

$$\left\{ (1+i)x(\cos[x] + i \sec[x]^2) - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x(\cos[x] + i \sec[x]^2)} + (i^{e^x} + e^x)(i \cos[x] + \sec[x]^2) + (1+i)(\sin[x] + i \tan[x]) - \frac{(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2})(x^{1/3} + ix)(\sin[x] + i \tan[x])}{\sqrt{(1+i)x}} - \left(i + \frac{1}{3x^{2/3}} \right) \sqrt{(1+i)x(\sin[x] + i \tan[x])} + \left(e^x + \frac{1}{2} i i^{e^x} e^x \pi \right) (i \sin[x] + \tan[x]) \right\}$$

$$\operatorname{Re}[(1+i)x(\sin[x] + i \tan[x]) - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x(\sin[x] + i \tan[x])} + (i^{e^x} + e^x)(i \sin[x] + \tan[x])],$$

$$\left\{ (1+i)x(\cos[x] + i \sec[x]^2) - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x(\cos[x] + i \sec[x]^2)} + (i^{e^x} + e^x)(i \cos[x] + \sec[x]^2) + (1+i)(\sin[x] + i \tan[x]) - \frac{(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2})(x^{1/3} + ix)(\sin[x] + i \tan[x])}{\sqrt{(1+i)x}} - \left(i + \frac{1}{3x^{2/3}} \right) \sqrt{(1+i)x(\sin[x] + i \tan[x])} + \left(e^x + \frac{1}{2} i i^{e^x} e^x \pi \right) (i \sin[x] + \tan[x]) \right\}$$

$$\operatorname{Im}[(1+i)x(\sin[x] + i \tan[x]) - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x(\sin[x] + i \tan[x])} + (i^{e^x} + e^x)(i \sin[x] + \tan[x])]$$

Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*(Csc[x] + I*Cot[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x)*(Cot[x] + I*Csc[x]) - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*(Csc[x] + I*Cot[x])]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Eq - 15c

In[7]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*(Csc[x] + I*Cot[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x)*(Cot[x] + I*Csc[x]) - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*(Csc[x] + I*Cot[x])]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Out[7]=

Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*(ArcSin[x] + I*ArcTan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x)*(ArcTan[x] + I*ArcSin[x]) - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*(ArcSin[x] + I*ArcTan[x])]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Eq - 15d

In[6]:= Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*(ArcSin[x] + I*ArcTan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x)*(ArcTan[x] + I*ArcSin[x]) - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*(ArcSin[x] + I*ArcTan[x])]], {x, -6., 6.}]

Out[6]=

$$\text{plot } \left\{ \text{Re}\left((1+i)(ix)(\sin(ix) + i \tan(ix)) - (ix + (ix)^{1/3}) \sqrt{(1+i)(ix)} (\sin(ix) + i \tan(ix)) + (i^{\sqrt{e^{ix}}} + e^{ix})(i \sin(ix) + \tan(ix))\right), \text{Im}\left((1+i)(ix)(\sin(ix) + i \tan(ix)) - (ix + (ix)^{1/3}) \sqrt{(1+i)(ix)} (\sin(ix) + i \tan(ix)) + (i^{\sqrt{e^{ix}}} + e^{ix})(i \sin(ix) + \tan(ix))\right) \right\}$$
 from $x = -6$. to 6 .

Eq - 15e

In[5]:=

```

Plot[{Re[(1 + I)*(I*x)*(Sin[I*x] + I*Tan[I*x]) - ((I*x)^(1/3) + I*(I*x))*Sqrt[(1 + I)*(I*x)]*
(Sin[I*x] + I*Tan[I*x]) + (I^E^I*x + E^I*x)*(I*Sin[I*x] + Tan[I*x])],
Im[(1 + I)*(I*x)*(Sin[I*x] + I*Tan[I*x]) - ((I*x)^(1/3) + I*(I*x))*Sqrt[(1 + I)*(I*x)]*
(Sin[I*x] + I*Tan[I*x]) + (I^E^I*x + E^I*x)*(I*Sin[I*x] + Tan[I*x])]}, {x, -6., 6.}]

```

Out[5]=


```
LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x)*(Tan[x] + I*Sin[x]) - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x])]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Eq - 15f

```
In[4]:= LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x)*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x)*(Tan[x] + I*Sin[x]) - (x^(1/3) + I*x)*Sqrt[x + I*x]*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x])]], {x, -6., 6.}]
```

Out[4]=


```
{(x+ix^2){sinx+itanx}+{e^x+i^e^x^2}{tanx+isinx}-{x^1/3+ix^2}*sqrt{x+ix^2}{sinx+itanx}}
```

Eq - 16

```
In[9]:= (x + I*x^2)*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*(Tan[x] + I*Sin[x]) - (x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x])
```

Out[9]=

$$-\left((x^{1/3} + ix^2) \sqrt{x + ix^2} (\sin[x] + i \tan[x])\right) + (x + ix^2) (\sin[x] + i \tan[x]) + (i^{e^{x^2}} + e^x) (i \sin[x] + \tan[x])$$

In[10]=

```
{(x+ix^2){sinx+itanx}+{e^x+i^e^x^2}{tanx+isinx}-{x^1/3+ix^2}*sqrt{x+ix^2}{sinx+itanx}}
```

Out[10]=

Assuming i is the imaginary unit | Use i as a **variable** instead

Input:

$$(x + ix^2) (\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) + (e^x + i^{e^{x^2}}) (\tan(x) + i \sin(x)) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + ix^2) \sqrt{x + ix^2} (\sin(x) + i \tan(x))$$

i is the imaginary unit »

Plots:

 min max

 min max

graph[[$x+ix^2$]{ $\sin x+i\tan x$ }+{ $e^x+i e^{x^2}$ }{ $\tan x+i\sin x$ } - { $x^{1/3}+ix^2$ }* $\sqrt{x+ix^2}$ }{ $\sin x+i\tan x$ }]

Eq - 16a

In[11]:= `Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*(Tan[x] + I*Sin[x]) - (x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x])]], {x, -6., 6.}]`

Out[11]=

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Eq - 16b} \\ \frac{d}{dx} \{ \text{Re}((x + i x^2) (\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) - (x^{1/3} + i x^2) \sqrt{x + i x^2}) \\ (\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) + (e^x + i^{e^{x^2}}) (\tan(x) + i \sin(x)), \\ \text{Im}((x + i x^2) (\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) - (x^{1/3} + i x^2) \sqrt{x + i x^2}) \\ (\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) + (e^x + i^{e^{x^2}}) (\tan(x) + i \sin(x)) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{In[16]:=} \\ D[\{\text{Re}[-((x^{1/3} + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x])) + \\ (x + I*x^2)*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x]) + (I^E^x + E^x)*(I*Sin[x] + Tan[x])], \\ \text{Im}[-((x^{1/3} + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x])) + \\ (x + I*x^2)*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x]) + (I^E^x + E^x)*(I*Sin[x] + Tan[x])]\}, x] \end{aligned}$$

Out[16]=

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\{ -\left((x^{1/3} + i x) \sqrt{x + i x} (\cos[x] + i \sec[x]) \right) + (x + i x) (\cos[x] + i \sec[x]) + \right. \\ & \quad \left(i^{e^{x^2}} + e^x \right) (i \cos[x] + \sec[x]) + (1 + 2 i x) (\sin[x] + i \tan[x]) - \frac{(1 + 2 i x) (x^{1/3} + i x) (\sin[x] + i \tan[x])}{2 \sqrt{x + i x}} - \\ & \quad \left(\frac{1}{3 x^{2/3}} + 2 i x \right) \sqrt{x + i x} (\sin[x] + i \tan[x]) + \left(e^x + i^{1+e^{x^2}} e^{x^2} \pi x \right) (i \sin[x] + \tan[x]) \right\} \\ & \text{Re}[-((x^{1/3} + i x^2) \sqrt{x + i x^2} (\sin[x] + i \tan[x])) + (x + i x^2) (\sin[x] + i \tan[x]) + (i^{e^{x^2}} + e^x) (i \sin[x] + \tan[x])], \\ & \left\{ -\left((x^{1/3} + i x^2) \sqrt{x + i x^2} (\cos[x] + i \sec[x]^2) \right) + (x + i x^2) (\cos[x] + i \sec[x]^2) + \right. \\ & \quad \left(i^{e^{x^2}} + e^x \right) (i \cos[x] + \sec[x]^2) + (1 + 2 i x) (\sin[x] + i \tan[x]) - \frac{(1 + 2 i x) (x^{1/3} + i x^2) (\sin[x] + i \tan[x])}{2 \sqrt{x + i x^2}} - \\ & \quad \left(\frac{1}{3 x^{2/3}} + 2 i x \right) \sqrt{x + i x^2} (\sin[x] + i \tan[x]) + \left(e^x + i^{1+e^{x^2}} e^{x^2} \pi x \right) (i \sin[x] + \tan[x]) \right\} \\ & \text{Im}[-((x^{1/3} + i x^2) \sqrt{x + i x^2} (\sin[x] + i \tan[x])) + (x + i x^2) (\sin[x] + i \tan[x]) + (i^{e^{x^2}} + e^x) (i \sin[x] + \tan[x])] \} \end{aligned}$$

```

Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*(Csc[x] + I*Cot[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*(Cot[x] + I*Csc[
x]) - (x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*(Csc[x] + I*Cot[x])]], {x, -6., 6.}]

```

Eq - 16c

In[15]:=

```

Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*(Csc[x] + I*Cot[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*(Cot[x] + I*Csc[x]) -
(x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*(Csc[x] + I*Cot[x])]], {x, -6., 6.}]

```

Out[15]=

— $\text{Re}\left(\left(i e^{x^2} + e^x\right)\left(\cot(x) + i \csc(x)\right) - \left(\sqrt[3]{x} + i x\right)\right)$
— $\text{Im}\left(\left(i e^{x^2} + e^x\right)\left(\cot(x) + i \csc(x)\right) - \left(\sqrt[3]{x} + i x\right)\right)$

```

Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*(ArcSin[x] + I*ArcTan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*(ArcTan[
x] + I*ArcSin[x]) - (x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*(ArcSin[x] + I*ArcTan[x])]], {x, -6.,
6.}]

```

Eq - 16d

In[14]:=

```

Plot[
Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*(ArcSin[x] + I*ArcTan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*(ArcTan[x] + I*ArcSin[x]) -
(x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*(ArcSin[x] + I*ArcTan[x])]], {x, -6., 6.}]

```

Out[14]=

— $\text{Re}\left(-\left(\sqrt[3]{x} + i x^2\right)\sqrt{x + i x^2}\left(\sin^{-1}(x) + i \tan^{-1}(x)\right)\right)$
— $\text{Im}\left(-\left(\sqrt[3]{x} + i x^2\right)\sqrt{x + i x^2}\left(\sin^{-1}(x) + i \tan^{-1}(x)\right)\right)$

$$\text{plot } \left\{ \text{Re}\left(\left(i (i x)^2 + i x\right) (\sin(i x) + i \tan(i x)) - \left(i (i x)^2 + (i x)^{1/3}\right) \sqrt{i (i x)^2 + i x} (\sin(i x) + i \tan(i x)) + \left(i^{e^{\left(i x\right)^2} + e^{i x}\right) (i \sin(i x) + \tan(i x))\right), \text{Im}\left(\left(i (i x)^2 + i x\right) (\sin(i x) + i \tan(i x)) - \left(i (i x)^2 + (i x)^{1/3}\right) \sqrt{i (i x)^2 + i x} (\sin(i x) + i \tan(i x)) + \left(i^{e^{\left(i x\right)^2} + e^{i x}\right) (i \sin(i x) + \tan(i x))\right) \right\} \text{ from } x = -6. \text{ to } 6.$$

Eq - 16e

In[13]:=

```

Plot[{Re[-((I*x)^(1/3) + I*(I*x)^2)*Sqrt[I*x + I*(I*x)^2]*(Sin[I*x] + I*Tan[I*x]) +
(I*x + I*(I*x)^2)*(Sin[I*x] + I*Tan[I*x]) + (I^E^(I*x)^2 + E^(I*x))*(I*Sin[I*x] + Tan[I*x])],
Im[-((I*x)^(1/3) + I*(I*x)^2)*Sqrt[I*x + I*(I*x)^2]*(Sin[I*x] + I*Tan[I*x]) + (I*x + I*(I*x)^2)*
(Sin[I*x] + I*Tan[I*x]) + (I^E^(I*x)^2 + E^(I*x))*(I*Sin[I*x] + Tan[I*x])}], {x, -6., 6.}]

```

Out[13]:=

E `LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*(Tan[x] + I*Sin[x]) - (x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x])]], {x, -6., 6.}]` Eq - 16f

In[12]:= `LogPlot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^2)*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x^2)*(Tan[x] + I*Sin[x]) - (x^(1/3) + I*x^2)*Sqrt[x + I*x^2]*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x])]], {x, -6., 6.}]`

Out[12]=

E `{{x+ix^3}{sinx+itanx}+{e^x+i^e^x^3}{tanx+isinx}-{x^1/3+ix^3}*sqrt{x+ix^3}{sinx+itanx}}` Eq - 17

In[17]:= `(x + I*x^3)*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*(Tan[x] + I*Sin[x]) - (x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x])`

Out[17]=

$$-\left((x^{1/3} + ix^3) \sqrt{x + ix^3} (\sin(x) + i \tan(x))\right) + (x + ix^3) (\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) + (i^{e^{x^3}} + e^x) (i \sin(x) + \tan(x))$$

In[18]=

E `[[{x+ix^3}{sinx+itanx}+{e^x+i^e^x^3}{tanx+isinx}]-{x^1/3+ix^3}*sqrt{x+ix^3}{sinx+itanx}]`

Out[18]=

Assuming i is the imaginary unit | Use i as a **variable** instead

Input:

$$(x + ix^3) (\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) + (e^x + i^{e^{x^3}}) (\tan(x) + i \sin(x)) - (\sqrt[3]{x} + ix^3) \sqrt{x + ix^3} (\sin(x) + i \tan(x))$$

i is the imaginary unit »

Plots:

min max

Alternate forms:

More

$$\frac{\left(e^x + i e^{x^3}\right) (\tan(x) + i \sin(x)) + (x + i x^3) (\cos(x) + i) \tan(x) - \left(\sqrt[3]{x} + ix^3\right) \sqrt{x+i x^3} (\cos(x) + i) \tan(x)}{i \sin(x)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\left(\sqrt[3]{x} + i x^3\right) \sqrt{x + i x^3} \left(\sin(x) + \frac{\sin(x)}{\cos(x)}\right) + \\
& (x + i x^3) \left(\sin(x) + \frac{i \sin(x)}{\cos(x)}\right) + \left(i^{e^x} + e^x\right) \left(i \sin(x) + \frac{\sin(x)}{\cos(x)}\right) \\
& -i \left(i \left(-x^3 + i^{e^x} + \sqrt{i x (x^2 - i)}\right) (x^{8/3} - i) \sqrt[3]{x} + i x + e^x\right) + \\
& \left(-x^3 + i^{e^x+2} + \sqrt{i x (x^2 - i)}\right) (x^{8/3} - i) \sqrt[3]{x} + i x - e^x \cos(x) \tan(x)
\end{aligned}$$

Expanded form: +

$$\begin{aligned}
& -i \sqrt{x + i x^3} x^3 \sin(x) + i x^3 \sin(x) - \sqrt{x + i x^3} \sqrt[3]{x} \sin(x) + i^{e^x+1} \sin(x) + \sqrt{x + i x^3} x^3 \tan(x) - \\
& x^3 \tan(x) - i \sqrt{x + i x^3} \sqrt[3]{x} \tan(x) + i^{e^x} \tan(x) + x \sin(x) + i e^x \sin(x) + i x \tan(x) + e^x \tan(x)
\end{aligned}$$

WolframAlpha +

Assuming i is the imaginary unit | Use i as a variable instead

Input: +

$$\begin{aligned}
& (x + i x^3) (\sin(x) + i \tan(x)) + (e^x + i^{e^x}) (\tan(x) + i \sin(x)) - \\
& (\sqrt[3]{x} + i x^3) \sqrt{x + i x^3} (\sin(x) + i \tan(x))
\end{aligned}$$

i is the imaginary unit »Plots: +min ▢ max ▢

Alternate forms:

More +

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(e^x + i^{e^{x^3}}\right) (\tan(x) + i \sin(x)) + (x + i x^3) (\cos(x) + i) \tan(x) - \\ & \left(\sqrt[3]{x} + i x^3\right) \sqrt{x + i x^3} (\cos(x) + i) \tan(x) \\ & - \left(\sqrt[3]{x} + i x^3\right) \sqrt{x + i x^3} \left(\sin(x) + \frac{i \sin(x)}{\cos(x)}\right) + \\ & (x + i x^3) \left(\sin(x) + \frac{i \sin(x)}{\cos(x)}\right) + \left(i^{e^{x^3}} + e^x\right) \left(i \sin(x) + \frac{\sin(x)}{\cos(x)}\right) \\ & - i \left(i \left(-x^3 + i^{e^{x^3}} + \sqrt{i x (x^2 - i)}\right) (x^{8/3} - i) \sqrt[3]{x} + i x + e^x\right) + \\ & \left(-x^3 + i^{e^{x^3}+2} + \sqrt{i x (x^2 - i)}\right) (x^{8/3} - i) \sqrt[3]{x} + i x - e^x \cos(x) \tan(x) \end{aligned}$$

Expanded form: +

$$\begin{aligned} & -i \sqrt{x + i x^3} x^3 \sin(x) + i x^3 \sin(x) - \sqrt{x + i x^3} \sqrt[3]{x} \sin(x) + \\ & i^{e^{x^3}+1} \sin(x) + \sqrt{x + i x^3} x^3 \tan(x) - x^3 \tan(x) - i \sqrt{x + i x^3} \sqrt[3]{x} \tan(x) + \\ & i^{e^{x^3}} \tan(x) + x \sin(x) + i e^x \sin(x) + i x \tan(x) + e^x \tan(x) \end{aligned}$$

WolframAlpha +

Eq - 17a

$$\text{graph}\left[\left\{x+ix^3\right\}\left\{\sin x+i \tan x\right\}+\left\{e^x+i e^x\right\}\left\{\tan x+i \sin x\right\}-\left\{x^{1/3}+ix^3\right\}\sqrt{\left\{x+ix^3\right\}\left\{\sin x+i \tan x\right\}}\right]$$

Eq - 17a

In[19]:=
$$\text{Plot}\left[\text{Evaluate}\left[\text{ReIm}\left[\left(x+I x^3\right)\left(\sin [x]+I \tan [x]\right)+\left(E^x+I E^x\right)\left(\tan [x]+I \sin [x]\right)-\left(x^{1/3}+I x^3\right)\sqrt{\left(x+I x^3\right)\left(\sin [x]+I \tan [x]\right)}\right],\{x,-6., 6.\}\right]$$

Out[19]=

Eq - 17b

$$\text{Plot}\left[\text{Evaluate}\left[\text{ReIm}\left[\left(x+I x^3\right)\left(\text{Csc}[x]+I \text{Cot}[x]\right)+\left(E^x+I E^x\right)\left(\text{Cot}[x]+I \text{Csc}[x]\right)-\left(x^{1/3}+I x^3\right)\sqrt{\left(x+I x^3\right)\left(\text{Csc}[x]+I \text{Cot}[x]\right)}\right],\{x,-6., 6.\}\right]$$

Eq - 17b

In[24]:=
$$\text{Plot}\left[\text{Evaluate}\left[\text{ReIm}\left[\left(x+I x^3\right)\left(\text{Csc}[x]+I \text{Cot}[x]\right)+\left(E^x+I E^x\right)\left(\text{Cot}[x]+I \text{Csc}[x]\right)-\left(x^{1/3}+I x^3\right)\sqrt{\left(x+I x^3\right)\left(\text{Csc}[x]+I \text{Cot}[x]\right)}\right],\{x,-6., 6.\}\right]$$

Out[24]=


```

Plot[Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*(ArcSin[x] + I*ArcTan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*(ArcTan[
x] + I*ArcSin[x]) - (x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*(ArcSin[x] + I*ArcTan[x])]], {x, -6.,
6.}]

```

Eq - 17c

In[23]:=

```

Plot[
Evaluate[ReIm[(x + I*x^3)*(ArcSin[x] + I*ArcTan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*(ArcTan[x] + I*ArcSin[x]) -
(x^(1/3) + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*(ArcSin[x] + I*ArcTan[x])]], {x, -6., 6.}]

```

Out[23]=

$$\text{plot} \left\{ \text{Re} \left((i (i x)^3 + i x) (\sin(i x) + i \tan(i x)) - (i (i x)^3 + (i x)^{1/3}) \sqrt{i (i x)^3 + i x} (\sin(i x) + i \tan(i x)) + (i^{e^((i x)^3)} + e^{(i x)}) (i \sin(i x) + \tan(i x))) \right), \text{Im} \left((i (i x)^3 + i x) (\sin(i x) + i \tan(i x)) - (i (i x)^3 + (i x)^{1/3}) \sqrt{i (i x)^3 + i x} (\sin(i x) + i \tan(i x)) + (i^{e^((i x)^3)} + e^{(i x)}) (i \sin(i x) + \tan(i x))) \right) \right\}$$
 from $x = -6.$ to $6.$

Eq - 17d

In[22]:=

```

Plot[{Re[-((I*x)^(1/3) + I*(I*x)^3)*Sqrt[I*x + I*(I*x)^3]*(Sin[I*x] + I*Tan[I*x])] +
      (I*x + I*(I*x)^3)*(Sin[I*x] + I*Tan[I*x]) + (I^E^(I*x)^3 + E^(I*x))*(I*Sin[I*x] + Tan[I*x])],
      Im[-((I*x)^(1/3) + I*(I*x)^3)*Sqrt[I*x + I*(I*x)^3]*(Sin[I*x] + I*Tan[I*x])] + (I*x + I*(I*x)^3)*
      (Sin[I*x] + I*Tan[I*x]) + (I^E^(I*x)^3 + E^(I*x))*(I*Sin[I*x] + Tan[I*x])}], {x, -6., 6.}]

```

Out[22]=

Eq - 17e

$$\text{LogPlot}[\text{Evaluate}[\text{ReIm}[(x + I*x^3)*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*(Tan[x] + I*Sin[x]) - (x^{1/3} + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x])]], \{x, -6., 6.\}]$$

In[20]:=
$$\text{LogPlot}[\text{Evaluate}[\text{ReIm}[(x + I*x^3)*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x]) + (E^x + I^E^x^3)*(Tan[x] + I*Sin[x]) - (x^{1/3} + I*x^3)*Sqrt[x + I*x^3]*(Sin[x] + I*Tan[x])]], \{x, -6., 6.\}]$$

Out[20]=

